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Item 3

Note on the use of the social-ecological indicator bundles approach

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Introduction

The following document describes work undertaken on using social-ecological indicator bundles. This note would be made available to IPBES experts as a resource.

I. Background

The complex interactions of nature and society are at the core of IPBES work, which covers a range of scientific disciplines, and encompasses a wide diversity of stakeholders as well as their knowledge systems¹. Approaches and methodologies employed in the assessments thus need to tackle the different dimensions of nature and society that are relevant to IPBES. In regard to the work on indicators in the context of IPBES, an approach is needed that allows to integrate (bring together) indicators that represent the various disciplines, different knowledge systems and world views as well as multiple conceptualizations of values, taking into account the needs of different stakeholders, sectors and genders and considering different scales. Such an approach should not only consider indicators that cover the six elements representing nature and society (the *boxes* of the IPBES conceptual framework), but also include indicators that speak to the interactions and influences between these elements (the *arrows* of the IPBES conceptual framework).

Building on work conducted by a group of experts under the guidance of the task force on knowledge and data, the Multidisciplinary Expert Panel in 2016 approved a list of core and highlighted indicators for use (where appropriate) in the Global and Regional Assessments of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services and the Assessment of Land Degradation and Restoration. At this stage, this list had been biased towards indicators representing nature, material nature's contributions to people, and direct drivers impacting on nature. Furthermore, the capacity of individual indicators to capture the complexities of underlying processes had been limited, and the list of indicators had not adequately represented non-material contributions of nature to people or reflect quality of life. To close this gap, a subgroup was created to identify and propose a list of complementary social-ecological indicators. The MEP noted, however, that it was not clear which narratives these indicators support, and how they are linked, and requested further

¹ Diaz et al., 2020. The IPBES conceptual framework – connecting nature and people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* **14**:1-16. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2014.11.002>

work. Indicators selected should further consider multiple knowledge systems and be relevant for both developing and developed countries.

To advance the work on socio-ecological indicators, three workshops were held in 2016 and 2017. The first, held under the guidance of MEP members and experts involved in the scoping of the values assessment proposed a way forward for indicator selection. This included the following steps: 1) recall the key questions asked by the IPBES assessments, 2) define the overarching conceptual approach and rationale, 3) identify cross-cutting issues, 4) initiate a wide search of indicators, and from these, 5) select a reduced set of indicators that informs on the narratives associated with the cross-cutting issues.

Participants also proposed three cross-cutting issues including sub-themes for further consideration: 1) Food-energy-water nexus, considering food security, energy security and water security; 2) Natural assets, in particular biodiversity and ecosystem services, and 3) SDGs, with specific regard to health and wellbeing, income, livelihoods and subsistence, and taking into account trade-offs, resilience, as well as sustainability and transformation.

The second workshop, conducted in the context of the expert group on values, was dedicated to developing the conceptual approach to develop bundles of indicators that cover the different *boxes* of the IPBES conceptual framework as well as the interactions (*arrows*) among them. The bundles of indicators also make the connection between overarching questions formulated in the scoping document and single indicators, and support encompassing narratives within assessment chapters and the Summaries for Policy Makers of assessments². The narratives were used to create a more comprehensive, socio-ecological perspective to the topics, and bring together a suite of indicators (“bundles”).

Based on a set of overarching questions developed for the global assessment, experts at the workshop formulated five seed narratives that grouped the key questions: 1) health; 2) food security and sovereignty; 3) biodiversity hotspots and protected areas; 4) telecoupling and 5) governance and global commons (focused on marine systems). Annex 1 provides examples of the suggested narratives and associated indicators.

The third workshop, organized by the task force on knowledge and data, aimed to pilot, test and further develop the approach for a specific narrative (food security) and to reflect and to provide guidance on the use of the methodology in future assessments³. In particular, participants developed a list of dimensions, sub-bundles and indicators related to the relationship between biodiversity and food: sustainable production, diversity and access, proposed a set of next steps for further development and use of the approach in the global assessment, and provided guidance on the use of socio-ecological bundles of indicators in future IPBES assessments².

The process illustrated that the two aspects of the approach (identification of themes and narratives, and selection of indicator bundles) are very valuable to the IPBES assessment process. The approach can support the policy-relevance and cohesiveness of key messages for the summary of policy makers.

II. Concepts and conceptualization

In IPBES assessments, messages and themes reflect all components of the conceptual framework across the assessment chapters as well as on the interlinkages and interactions among the different components (boxes) of the IPBES conceptual framework. The themes and messages are supported by bundles of indicators that provides information or evidence underpinning the different social and ecological aspects of these messages.

² IPBES 2017. Outcome Document: Workshop on IPBES indicators from a socio-ecological perspective. Budapest, Hungary, 6 and 7 April 2017

³ IPBES 2017. Report of the IPBES workshop on social-ecological bundles of indicators: Assessing the relationship between biodiversity and food: sustainable production, diversity and access. Seoul, Republik of Korea, 5 -7 December 2017

Indicators

Indicators are understood as data, aggregated quantitatively or qualitatively, that reflect the status, cause or outcome of an object or process, and are used in the understanding that they can simplify complexity. Further, indicators complement other forms of information and knowledge. In the narrative approach, indicators tackle not only the different dimensions relevant to IPBES but also the boxes and arrows of the IPBES conceptual framework. In the socio-ecological bundles approach, indicators are complemented by other types of evidence, such as case studies, indications from conceptual research, maps or images.

Narratives

Narratives are in this context defined as “*policy-relevant story lines on specific topics that are supported by evidence in various chapters of an assessment and feature in their summary for policymakers*”¹. Narratives facilitates the addressing of complex issues, by giving broad, comprehensive social-ecological perspectives on the assessment topics, and take multiple knowledge and value systems into consideration.

Bundles

Bundles are “*system[s] of indicators that refer to the different elements of complex socio-ecological systems and of the IPBES conceptual framework, the interactions among them, the perspectives of different types of stakeholders on these elements and interactions, as well as different knowledge systems, thus encompassing different types of data*”¹. Bundles of indicators are built around a theme, which represents a societal and policy-relevant issue that has various relevant dimensions, aspects of which can be supported by evidence.

Socio-ecological bundles of indicators are groups of indicators and interlinked non-measurable knowledge and insights, that refer to the different elements of complex socio-ecological systems (and of the IPBES conceptual framework). They capture the interactions among the different elements, the perspectives of different stakeholders on these elements and interactions, as well as different knowledge systems, and thus encompass different types of data in specific socioecological and socioeconomic settings.

Bundles of indicators therefore address cross-cutting themes and their multiple dimensions at multiple scales, and are supported by a number of data sources. Rather than focusing on silver bullet indicators, the bundles approach would aim to overcome the limitations of any independent indicator by gathering different sources of information that would complement each other to together describe the complexities of the interlinkages and interactions among nature and people, the underlying processes.

An ideal bundle contains indicators that are drawn from various disciplines and knowledge systems, reflect various world views and conceptualisations of values, and speak to the needs of different stakeholders, sectors, gender, as well as different scales. Such ideal bundles would incorporate different types of data and knowledge (e.g. quantitative vs qualitative), different knowledge systems, different conceptualizations of the links between people and nature, different dimensions of value linked to such interactions and/or data with different type of coverage of the issues at stake (e.g. a map allowing for a global coverage vs. a box drawing on an in depth study case).

Notably, in a bundle of indicators, there might be some potentially measurable indicators which are identified yet the data is not available. In that way, a bundle approach helps to identify knowledge gaps.

III. Implementation of the approach in IPBES assessments

“Start with the end in mind”, that is, the development of the main messages to be included in the summary for policy makers and the identification of major relevant questions to prioritize for evaluation and review. This gives direction to authors and the teams conducting the analyses and increases the evidence base used for the summary of policy makers. Adjust the outline of summary during the course of the assessment to reflect / match the reality of the evidence. Table 1 provides an overview over a workflow for the implementation of the approach throughout the assessment process.

Table 1. Workflow for the implementation of the approach throughout the assessment process. Adapted from recommendations provided by experts participating in the Seoul Workshop December 2017⁴.

Assessment Stage	Steps taken to implement approach	Participants
Assessment scoping	Develop key questions, main messages and major themes	Scoping experts
Preparation of first author meeting	Refine key questions Identify preliminary themes and associated overarching questions for use across chapters Ensure necessary expertise across disciplines, data types and knowledge systems, fill gaps where necessary	Management Committee of Assessment Assessment Co-Chairs
First author meeting	Discuss and refine preliminary themes and overarching questions Identify sub-themes for each chapter Identify bundles of socio-economic and ecological key indicators, using the IPBES conceptual framework as a guide. Identify existing data related to the indicators, as well as required analyses	Assessment experts
Review of ZOD	Review themes and overarching questions Review indicator bundles Suggest additional indicators	Expert reviewers
Second author meeting	Review themes and key questions Identify indicator bundles Add new key questions and associated indicator bundles, where appropriate	Assessment experts
Review of FOD	Review themes and overarching questions Review indicator bundles	Expert reviewers
Third author meeting	Refine and finalise themes and overarching questions Refine and finalise indicator bundles	Assessment experts

The selection of seed narratives takes place during the content development of the assessment chapters. Seed narratives reflect the broad key themes of the assessment, guide the selection of indicators relevant to the narratives, and express the complexities around the key themes.

A 4-step approach is employed to identify narratives, indicators and indicator bundles (Figure 1). Note that this is an iterative and evolving and contextual (setting based) process - bundles grow and can be adapted throughout the stages of the assessment.

⁴ IPBES 2017. Report of the IPBES workshop on social-ecological bundles of indicators: Assessing the relationship between biodiversity and food: sustainable production, diversity and access. Seoul, Republik of Korea, 5 -7 December 2017

Figure 1: Illustration of the 4-step process to build narratives, identify indicators and create indicator bundles. Modified from Budapest Workshop Report⁵.

1. Identify seed narrative (key theme/topic)

These build on the overarching key questions as spelled out in the scoping document and cover potentially relevant aspects of the assessment. The seed narratives guide the selection of indicators required to express the complexities around the themes. Narratives cover more than one box or arrow of the IPBES conceptual framework; they speak to multiple knowledge systems and represent the complexity inherent to nature's contributions to people.

2. Selection of relevant indicators

When identifying and selecting indicators (and complementary materials, a number of different aspects need to be considered in the selection of indicators (Table 2).

⁵ IPBES 2017. Outcome Document: Workshop on IPBES indicators from a socio-ecological perspective. Budapest, Hungary, 6 and 7 April 2017

Table 2. Considerations for selection of Indicators.

Aspect	Indicator selection
Contribution to the area of the IPBES conceptual framework	Indicators for each box and arrow of the framework Indicators drawn from a variety of disciplines and sources
Relevance to a range of different stakeholders and end users	Indicators are relevant to a range of stakeholders and end users Indicators illustrate and communicate key points
Representation and reflection of multiple knowledge systems, world views and values	Indicators drawn from a variety of disciplines and sources Indicators used in management Indicators used in ILK assessments
Relevance	Indicators that are relevant for different <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● scales, from local to global ● types of data (e.g. quantitative vs qualitative), ● knowledge systems, ● conceptualizations of the links between people and nature, ● dimensions of value linked to such interactions and/or ● data with different type of coverage of the issues at stake (e.g. global coverage vs. In depth study case)- ● settings (ecological, socioeconomic, indigenous)

Gaps in indicators can be addressed by bringing in relevant experts to complement the existing array of indicators, by drawing from the pool of indicators used in previous assessments and complementing these further to fill gaps (NB: these should adhere to the criteria set out by the task force on knowledge and data). Indicators that are applied in other multilateral environmental agreements, e.g. SDG's, Post2020 Global Biodiversity Framework or the Sendai Framework can also be considered.

3. Recognize key indicators and their links to key aspects of the topic

From the list of indicators assembled in step 2., identify sub-sets (“bundles”) based on the following criteria:

- Contribution to the socio-ecological narrative for the topic
- Usefulness of the indicators for ongoing assessments
- Relevance of indicators for future monitoring
- Reflect interdependence, feedback loops and trade-offs

These bundles may be drawn from the existing IPBES list of core and highlighted indicators, but also from other data sources, that help to show status, trends and interlinkages (e.g. feedback loops), and can inform on the different perspectives of any one particular issue (e.g. different world views, different stakeholders, different knowledge systems). Key aspects in the themes, for which there are no indicators currently available, and for which status and trends have to be searched for in other ways, could also be identified. Gaps could also be identified, and additional experts brought on board in a timely fashion as authors. Relevant data providers would be identified at an early stage, partnerships built and syntheses based on existing data could be conducted. A categorization of indicators in sub-bundles can help to bring together a range of indicators in support of a specific message. Indicators can be part of multiple sub-bundles.

Experts at the Budapest Workshop proposed *Health, Food Security and Sovereignty, Biodiversity Hotspots and protected areas, Telecoupling* and *Global Commons (focused on marine ecosystems)* as seed narratives grouping the 25 key questions of the Global Assessments. Using the 4-step approach outlined above (see Figure 1), experts identified indicators for each of these key themes. They then narrowed these indicators to a subset of indicators, judging their contribution to the socio-ecological narrative for the

topic, their usefulness for the assessment, and relevance for future monitoring of the topic. Interdependence and trade-offs among indicators were also considered. Figure 3 illustrates how indicators contributing to a theme are distributed across the IPBES conceptual framework.

Figure 3. Placement of indicators supporting the seed narrative *Food Security and Sovereignty* across the IPBES conceptual framework. Adapted from Budapest Workshop Report⁶.

Indicators used: 1) Knowledge of Food diversity, 2) Rate of non-communicable diseases, 3) Percentage of malnutrition, 4) Household dietary diversity, 5) Household food groups, 6) Estimated fisheries catch and fishing effort, 7) Inland fisheries production, 8) Diversity and stability of food production, 9) Machinery and equipment, 10) Trends in pesticide use, 11) Fertilizer use, 12) Percentage of irrigated land, 13) Trends in fisheries certified by Marine Stewardship Council, 14) Trends in potentially harmful subsidies in agriculture, 15) Trends in potentially harmful subsidies in fisheries, 16) Consumption per capita, 17) Area under Bt crops, 18) Rate of consumption, 19) Total human population, 20) Proportion of local breeds classified as being at risk, 21) Proportion of fish stocks within biologically sustainable levels.

4. Build a narrative

⁶ IPBES 2017. Outcome Document: Workshop on IPBES indicators from a socio-ecological perspective. Budapest, Hungary, 6 and 7 April 2017

The narrative is built using the complete bundle of indicators identified in step 3, tying all indicators together, and considering:

- Elements relevant across all (most) chapters of the assessment
- Policy relevant messages
- Reflection of the complexity of the topic
- Evidence gathered by the bundles of indicators

The narrative (and the indicator bundles it is built on) should adequately cover all elements of the IPBES conceptual framework. The narrative should also be carried across all chapters of an assessment, keeping in mind that the narrative does not have to be represented solely through (global) indicators included in the bundles. It can also be supported by case studies, images, maps, or indicators that are available e.g. at regional and local scales only.

The use of *Food Security and Sovereignty* as a central narrative in the Global Assessment allows to reflect on a paradoxical situation relating to the trade-offs associated to food production (See Box 1). Although formal institutions in many regions of the world are geared towards optimizing food production, there are issues related to food distribution and malnutrition. The narrative allows to connect food, health and nature, for example linking to co-production of NCP, or the impact of food production as a driver of anthropogenic change on nature. The narrative enables the inclusion of all elements of the IPBES conceptual framework and their interactions.

Box 1: Example narrative for *Food Security and Sovereignty*. From Budapest Workshop Report.

Food security is a key constituent of *Good Quality of Life*. This is reflected for example on the extent of adequate nutrition status (*Ind. 1, 2, 3*), and on the rights to eat and decide what to eat, consume and produce. Nutrition in turn depends directly on the co-production of NCP (material & non-material) which occurs through the mix of *Anthropogenic assets* (*Ind. 9, 10, 11, 12*) and *Nature* (*Ind. 20, 21*), and involves productivity, stability of yields and diversity of production of crops, cattle, and fish among other NCP. Non-material NCP are related to the concept of ‘foodways’ where socio-cultural aspects of food are as important as issues of production and consumption. However, indicators reflecting elements such as food-identity are often hard to find in the literature. The degree of access to food links *NCP* to *Good Quality of Life* (*Ind. 4, 5*), while policies are often placed in *Institutions* acting as indirect drivers of changes in nature (*Ind. 13, 14, 15*), within which diverse worldviews and values can be more or less represented (policies towards optimising food productivity at the expense of stability, social relations through food). The capacity of nature itself to provide food is also affected by *Direct drivers of change*, which can either be natural or anthropogenic (*Ind. 16, 17, 18, 19*).

The narrative was further unpacked to identify the various dimensions of the relationship between biodiversity and food that were of relevance to the IPBES conceptual framework and the IPBES Global Assessment: sustainable production, access to food, and food diversity. Three nested levels of the theme were identified – food co-production, food security and food sovereignty - and used as basis for further analysis. Each of the themes were further split into main dimensions (bundles) and sub-bundles, for which the most appropriate indicators as well as alternative sources of information such as case studies were identified. Annex II – VI of the Seoul Workshop Report⁷ provide an overview over the complete list of ideal indicators associated with each of the bundles.

⁷ IPBES 2017. Report of the IPBES workshop on social-ecological bundles of indicators: Assessing the relationship between biodiversity and food: sustainable production, diversity and access. Seoul, Republik of Korea, 5 -7 December 2017